

ROLE OF THE STATE IN ENSURING MACROECONOMIC STABILITY

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Macroeconomic stability politics, country economy in keeping practical events process is considered This is in politics main purpose, economic stability and of loyalty preservation of capitalism in order inflation to reduce, spend economic reforms perform and workplace to create help is to give.

That is, it can be established in all areas of the main expenses, incomes and tax system of the country's economy. Part of the policy includes creating needed jobs, hiring, and reducing debt levels for students. Another part is aimed at regulating capitalism and reducing inflation, which is against this system.

In addition, macroeconomic stability policy is a public policy that integrates separate sectors of the economy and tries to create interdependence. The main objective of the policy is to increase economic activity, create jobs and generally ensure stability.

In order to ensure macroeconomic stability, countries should focus on important economic issues. They have to look at a number of big issues like markets, investment, trade demand, cash flow and other economic indicators.

In particular, the policy of macroeconomic stability makes it possible for countries to move from less advantaged sources to commercial markets, to create production and commercial relations with other countries. This, along with the work that provides an opportunity to acquire higher education, the right to study and prepare valuable professional skills, will bring stability to the scientific, social, economic and political development of the country.

That is, it means that it is possible to be continuous and stable in the economy. Macroeconomics, general economic indicators and economic stability topics can be counted among the main directions of economics in the country of samples. This concept is used to express the difference between macroeconomics and microeconomics. Macroeconomic indicators are the total volume of trade, national monetary income, employment, community size, national customs products or customers per person¹. They are not indicators that allow us to act in the micro economy, but are a sign to distinguish the general situation in the economy of all countries.

In order to determine the role of the state in ensuring macroeconomic stability, it is necessary to determine whether there is any influence on macroeconomic indicators and how to improve and improve these indicators.

Key macroeconomic indicators are used to measure the performance of the economy as a whole. Below are the most common indicators and their calculation methods (Table 1):

Table 1

Macroeconomic indicators and their calculation methods²

Macroeconomics

² Scientific from sources used without the author by Created

No	Main macroeconomic indicators	Description	Count them
1	Gross Domestic Product (GDP) ³	It is the total value of all goods and services produced within the borders of a country during a certain period of time, usually a quarter or a year. It is calculated by adding the final prices of all goods and services produced .	$GDP = C + I + G + (XM)$ Here: _ C = House of farms consumption expenses I = enterprises by investments G = State expenses X = Export M = Import
2	Inflation level	This is in the economy goods and services of the price time pass with growth speed _ Inflation measure wide spread out method is this home farms by buy removable goods and services in the basket of prices to change measuring consumption prices tracking index (CPI) .	$Inflation\ level = ((\text{current CPI in the past year} - \text{CPI in the year}) / \text{past CPI in the year}) * 100$
3	Unemployment level	It's useless , though active respectively the work looking for in the economy worker of strength share _ The work power when you say the work busy with or active the work those looking for understood	$Unemployment\ level = (\text{Unemployed workers Number} / \text{Worker power}) * 100$
4	State budget shortage	It is known time between, usually one year inside state expenses and income between difference _	$State\ budget\ deficit = \text{State expenses} - \text{State income}$
5	Payment balance	this country of the world the rest countries with all economic operations generalizing is a statement	He is two from the component consists of: Current account balance = Sales balance (export - import) + from abroad received pure income + net current transfers Capital account balance = Local to assets foreign

			ownership change - to foreign assets local ownership change .
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These are of the economy efficiency measure for used main macroeconomic of indicators one how many A lot more things there is and their each one of the economy different aspects about important concepts gives _

Macroeconomic stability in providing of the state role about in short:

1. Macroeconomic stability what

Macroeconomic stability, country (of the country economy) in the economy all of systems efficient management , development output , income and tax systems management of inflation another from declines not at all do not change , work place create , produce release and income increase control to do and institutional structures to create directed economic is politics .

2. Macroeconomic stability policy

Macroeconomic stability politics, economic to stability reach for practical of events is the basis. States unique state policies, budget policies and finance policies with together work will be released. them done from raising the goal this politics cooperation through country in the economy faithfulness and sincerity save stay, capitalism in order inflation to reduce, spend economic reforms done increase and the work place to create help to give the goal is to do States Macroeconomic stability in providing the following main measures perform:

- Finance policy
- State expenses and lending policy
- Budget policy.

As a result, countries macroeconomic of stability to himself characteristics learning their essence, qualities and symbol their understanding it is necessary It helps politics done in raising requirements and requirements answer of giving common to the situation looking politics changes and addition indicators apply necessary

State stable economic to grow provide low inflation level save stay, unemployment reduce and international trade stabilization policy done increase through macroeconomic stability in providing solution doer role plays

Macroeconomic to stability reach for state money and credit and tax budget policy mixed use need _ Money and credit policy prices stabilization for money mass and percentage rates in order to put directed if so, fiscal politics while expenses and revenues between balance storage for state expenses and to tax to pull directed.

State as well as international economic events attention with watching to go and surface coming each how to problems objectively in relation to be need. From this besides, investments, technological innovations and competitiveness encourage macroeconomic stability in storage important important have.

Summary by doing in other words, the state reasonable economic policy, effective in order put and reasonable financial management through macroeconomic to stability in reaching important role plays _ This is the economy stable to be, entrepreneurship of subjects in growth continue that it will and of citizens marriage level high to be provides.

So Macroeconomic of stability in providing of the state role very important. Because of this,

the state economic in the field all parties encourage for good policies and decisions acceptance to do need. Also the state economic in the field from the news use, international organizations with cooperation to do and another indicators own into will receive things done to increase need of the state economic in the field international organizations with cooperation and they are with transactional relationships too _ important _ This is international organizations with work through economic in the field another from countries experiences to receive, from the news to use and to them help to give provides.

References:

1. Абел Е., Бернанке Б. Макроэкономика. 5-е изд.- СПб.: Питер, 2008. – 768 с
2. Агапова Т.А., Серегина С.Ф. Макроэкономика. Учебник. 7- е изд. - М.: «Дело и Сервис», 2005. - 464 с.
3. Axmedov D.Q., Ishmuhamedov A.E., Jumayev Q.X., Djumayev Z.A. Макроиқтисодиёт. - Т.: «O'zbekiston yozuvchilar uyushmasining Adabiyot jamg_armasi nashriyoti», 2004 - 240 b.
4. Alan Grinspen. Эпоха потрясениу. Проблемы и перспективы мировоу финансовоу системы. -М.: Alpina Biznes Books, 2008. – 528с
5. Вечканов Г.С., Вечканова Г.Р. Макроэкономика; Учебник для вузов, 3-е изд., дополненное. - СПб.: Питер, 2009.- 350 с. 16. Вахобов А.В. va boshq. Xorijiy investitsiyalar. - Т.: Moliya, 2010 у.-328 b.
6. Akramovna, O. N. (2022, October). SCIENTIFIC ON INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF CROP PRODUCTION ON FARMS AND PEOPLE'S HOMESTEADS RECOMMENDATION ANALYSIS. In " *ONLINE-CONFERENCES*" PLATFORM (pp. 300-303).
7. Очилова, Н. А. (2023). Динамика Развития Дехканского И Подсобного Хозяйства Кашкадарьинской Области. *Innovative Society: Problems, Analysis and Development Prospects (Spain)*, 72-77.